

ASSESSMENT OF MICROBIOLOGICAL PURITY OF CLARY SAGE LEAVES (SALVIA SACLAREA L.)

Eshnazarova N.H.**Pulatova D.K.****Urmanova F.F.**

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: flyuraurmanova8@gmail.com

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Relevance: *Salvia L.* (sage) is one of the largest genera of the Lamiaceae family. Plants of this genus have long been used in folk and traditional medicine in various countries to relieve pain, protect against oxidative stress, free radical damage, angiogenesis, inflammation, as well as bacterial and viral infections. They are grown due to their aromatic properties for the production of food additives and essential oils, pharmaceuticals, dyes, cosmetics and biocides. The substances isolated from them are characterized by significant cytotoxic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiviral, antiplasmodial, antiplatelet aggregation, growth-inhibiting and repellent activity. One of the potential sources of biologically active substances with valuable pharmacological properties is the object of our research, clary sage (*Salvia saclarea L.*).

The purpose of the study. Taking into account that herbal medicines that are not sterilized during the manufacturing process can be contaminated with microorganisms, we have studied the microbiological frequency of a new medicinal plant of the domestic flora, clary sage, in order to introduce it into medical practice.

Materials and methods. The object of the study was the leaves of clary sage harvested during the flowering period from botanically reliable plants in the village of Chimgan, Tashkent region. The tests were carried out under aseptic conditions in accordance with the instructions of the State Pharmacopoeia of Uzbekistan. It included quantitative determination of viable bacteria and fungi, as well as identification of microorganisms, the presence of which is unacceptable in non-sterile medicines.

Results. Table 1 summarizes the results of a study of the microbiological purity of clary sage leaves.

Таблица 1

№	Indicators	HD Requirements	Analysis results	HD compliance
1.	Total number of aerobic bacteria (in 1 g of the preparation)	No more than 10^5	220 KOE	Respond
2.	Total number of yeast and mold fungi (per 1 g of preparation)	No more than 10^4	80 KOE	Respond
3.	Group of Entobacteriaceae (<i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i>), <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Must be missing	Missing	Respond

It follows from the above data that the leaves of clary sage fully comply with the requirements for the microbiological purity of plant raw materials.

Conclusions. Studies have been conducted to assess the microbiological purity of raw materials of clary sage leaves. The data obtained will be in demand when developing appropriate regulatory documentation for it.